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CONTENTS

A REPORT ON INTER-GENERIC MATING BETWEEN COMMON CROW <i>EUPLOEA CORE</i> AND GREAT EGGFLY <i>HYPOLIMNAS BOLINA</i> BUTTERFLIES FROM KHATRA, BANKURA, WEST BENGAL, INDIA by Santanu Bag & Abinash Dey.....	1
PARASITOIDS OF THE GALL-INDUCER INSECT FROM <i>GARUGA PINNATA</i> ROXB.: A REPORT FROM SOUTHERN KARNATAKA by Lakshmi C R, Sowmya T N, Basavarajappa S& Nalini M S	4
FIRST RECORD OF RINGED CASCADER <i>ZYGONYX TORRIDUS</i> KIRBY, 1889 DRAGONFLY FROM WEST BENGAL, INDIA by Adarsha Mukherjee, Supriya Mahato & Supriya Samanta.....	10
FIRST RECORD OF SOLIFUGAE (RHAGODIDAE AND GALEODIDAE) FROM DELHI, INDIA by Durga Prasad Srivastava, Aditya Singh Chauhan, Faiyaz A. Khudsar & Mayanglambam Ojit Kumar Singh.....	14
CONFIRMATION OF INDIAN OAKBLUE <i>ARHOPALA ATRAX</i> (HEWITSON, 1862) (LEPIDOPTERA: LYCAENIDAE) FROM SOUTHERN UTTAR PRADESH, INDIA by Harendra Srivastava.....	24
REDISCOVERY OF THE KASHMIR MEADOWBROWN BUTTERFLY (<i>HYPONEPHELE CHEENA KASHMIRICA</i>) FROM JAMMU & KASHMIR, INDIA by Sadam H Malik, Inayat Ullah Lone & Sajad Ahmad Khan.....	26
<i>CYNANCHUM CALLIALATUM</i> : A PUTATIVE NEW LARVAL FOOD PLANT OF THE PLAIN TIGER <i>DANAUS CHRYSIPPUS</i> (LEPIDOPTERA: NYMPHALIDAE) FROM AN ECO-RESTORATION SITE OF PUNE, MAHARASHTRA, INDIA by Chintan Bhatt, Pratik Purohit & Arajush Payra.....	30
FIRST RECORD OF <i>AZANUS UBALDUS</i> (STOLL, 1782) (INSECTA: LEPIDOPTERA: LYCAENIDAE) FROM JHARKHAND, INDIA by Suraj Kumar Singha Deo, Debasish Mahato & Rishav Singha Deo.....	33
ADDITION OF THE RED PIERROT BUTTERFLY <i>TALICADA NYSEUS NYSEUS</i> TO THE BUTTERFLY FAUNA OF CHHATTISGARH, INDIA by Saurabh Singh, Gulab Chand, Ravi Naidu, Gulshan Kumar, Ramanand Agrawal, & H. N. Tandan.....	36
STUDIES ON FORAGING AND POLLINATING ACTIVITY OF DWARF HONEY BEE (<i>APIS FLOREA</i> F.) ON BLOOMS OF <i>BRASSICA JUNCEA</i> LINNAEUS IN WEST BENGAL, INDIA by Amit Kumar Gayen & Narayan Ghorai.....	39

A NEW ALTITUDINAL RECORD FOR THE BLUE PANSY BUTTERFLY <i>JUNONIA ORITHYA</i> FROM BHUTAN by Sonam Lhaki Dema.....	45
GREAT EGGFLY BUTTERFLIES <i>HYPOLIMNAS BOLINA</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758) (LEPIDOPTERA: NYMPHALIDAE) FEEDING ON PUMPKIN FRUIT IN NEPAL by Karuna Pandey & Bibek Gyawali.....	47
NEW ALTITUDE RANGE OF <i>CLELEA DISCRIMINIS</i> SWINHOE, 1891 (LEPIDOPTERA: ZYGAENIDAE) IN ASSAM, INDIA by Monish Kumar Thapa, Priyanku Borah, Hirakjyoti Das & Ritu Kalita.....	49
NEW REPORT OF <i>SCROBIGERA ALBOMARGINATA</i> (MOORE, 1867) (LEPIDOPTERA: NOCTUIDAE) FROM SOUTHERN MYANMAR by Than Than Aung & Min Khant Naing.....	51
EARLY EMERGENCE OF <i>CYPA DECOLOR</i> (LEPIDOPTERA: SPHINGIDAE) IN THE KUMAON HIMALAYA by Vishal Potdar & Surendra Pariyar.....	53
BLUE GLASSY TIGER <i>IDEOPSIS SIMILIS PERSIMILIS</i> (MOORE 1879) (LEPIDOPTERA: NYMPHALIDAE)- FIRST RECORD FROM DEHING PATKAI NATIONAL PARK, ASSAM by Monish Kumar Thapa & Rituraj Bhuyan.....	55
NEW DISTRIBUTION RECORD OF <i>EUASPA MILIONIA</i> HEWITSON, 1869 (LEPIDOPTERA: LYCAENIDAE: THECLINAE) FROM SIKKIM, INDIA by Sonam Wangchuk Lepcha, Mingdup Lepcha, Nosang Muringla Limboo, Sonam Pintso Sherpa, Sonam Wangchik Lepcha Jr. & Monish Kumar Thapa.....	57
<i>LILIUM LONGIFLORUM</i> AND <i>LILIUM BULBIFERUM</i> (LILIACAE): NEW LARVAL HOST PLANTS FOR <i>KANISKA CANACE</i> (LEPIDOPTERA: NYMPHALIDAE) FROM ARUNACHAL PRADESH, INDIA by Ruksha Limbu & Roshan Upadhaya.....	60
MALE <i>ARHOPALA</i> BOISDUVAL, 1832 (LEPIDOPTERA: LYCAENIDAE) HIBERNATE IN THE KUMAON HIMALAYA, INDIA by Peter Smetacek & Amaan Sayed.....	65
CONFIRMATION OF THE COMMON EARL <i>TANAECIA JULII</i> (LEPIDOPTERA: NYMPHALIDAE) IN KUMAON, UTTARAKHAND, INDIA by Jagdish Bhatt.....	67
NEW ADDITIONS TO THE CHECKLIST OF BUTTERFLIES OF CORBETT TIGER RESERVE, UTTARAKHAND, INDIA by Rajesh Chaudhary, Manoj Sharma, Sanjay Chhimwal & Vinesh Kumar.....	69
THE FIRST PHOTOGRAPHIC EVIDENCE OF PARTIAL ALBINISM IN A HOUSE SPARROW <i>PASSER DOMESTICUS</i> IN INDIA by Deepak Kumar.....	75
SYNONYMY OF <i>TELCHINIA ISSORIA ISSORIA</i> AND <i>TELCHINIA ISSORIA ANOMALA</i> (LEPIDOPTERA: NYMPHALIDAE: ACRAEINAE) by Peter Smetacek, Than Than Aung ² , Bharati & Shilpa.....	79

FIRST RECORDS OF 25 SKIPPERS (LEPIDOPTERA:HESPERIIDAE) FOR BHUTAN AND
CONFIRMATION OR RECENT EVIDENCE OF 25 SELDOM REPORTED SKIPPERS by
Piet Van Der Poel, Karma Wangdi & Sajan Kc.....83

BLUE GLASSY TIGER *IDEOPSIS SIMILIS PERSIMILIS* (MOORE 1879) (LEPIDOPTERA: NYMPHALIDAE)- FIRST RECORD FROM DEHING PATKAI NATIONAL PARK, ASSAM

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ABSTRACT

The present note reports the first confirmed record of *Ideopsis similis persimilis* from the Dehing Patkai National Park, Assam. Possibly, this report is the second record for India.

KEYWORDS: Danainae, Blue Glassy Tiger, New Record, Dehing Patkai, Assam

INTRODUCTION

The Blue Glassy Tiger *Ideopsis similis persimilis* (Moore 1879) is common throughout its range. It is widespread across Myanmar, southern China, Thailand, Laos, Cambodia, Vietnam, Malaysia, Sumatra (Yutaka, 2015) and Sri Lanka (Evans, 1932). The genus *Ideopsis* (Horsfield, 1829) includes two species found in India (Varshney & Smetacek, 2015). Out of these two species *Ideopsis similis* is the only species reported from Northeast India, specifically Arunachal Pradesh (Thombre & Kehimkar, 2015). The other species, *Ideopsis juvena nicobarica*, is found in the Nicobar Islands (Varshney & Smetacek, 2015).

There are no recent records of *I. similis* from India after Thombre and Kehimkar (2015). Das *et al.* (2017) prepared an updated list of butterflies of Dibru-Saikhuwa National Park, Assam but they did not find *I. similis* in the area. Singh (2017), who studied and reviewed the butterflies of Eastern Assam, which includes Dehing Patkai National Park (DPNP), did not record this species. Recently, Gogoi *et al.* (2023) studied the diversity and specific richness of butterfly in DPNP, but did not report this species.

RESULT

The current record is from an opportunistic survey conducted at Soraipung Division, Dehing Patkai National Park, Assam on April 30, 2023, at around 10:24 hrs. We observed more than four individuals of the species and photographed one while the butterfly was basking in the sun. The habitat, where the butterflies were sighted consists of evergreen shrubs located at coordinates 27.356009 N and 95.539782 E.

I. similis was recorded by Thombre & Kehimkar (2015) from Namdapha National Park, Arunachal Pradesh and that was the first and only record for India so far. Therefore, probably this record will be the second record for India and first report from Assam.

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Figure 1: Underside of *Ideopsis similis persimilis* recorded in this study.

Figure 2: Upperside of *Ideopsis similis persimilis* as above.